
Taraba State Based Journalists Perception of Investigative Journalism as an Antidote to Institutional Corruption in Nigeria

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Abstract

The researchers examined the use of investigative journalism in combating institutional corruption in Nigeria. It investigated the challenges affecting investigative journalists in curbing institutional corruption in Nigeria. The researchers employed the social responsibility theory which posited that the mass media have a duty to serve the public interest by providing accurate and unbiased information, promoting democratic values and holding those in power accountable. The researchers adopted a qualitative approach where an in-depth interview was employed alongside 20 journalists from a population of 100 from six chapters within Jalingo metropolis who write for the various news organisations in the State. The findings of the study revealed that journalists in Taraba State have misconceptions regarding what institutional corruption entails which has affected their fight against institutional corruption. Also, it was established that challenges such as fear of the unknown, harassment, lack of access to information, lack of funds and widespread corruption within the media amongst others. The researchers recommended among others that there is need for journalists to be enlightened on what institutional corruption entails through organising seminars and symposiums. It further recommended that journalists should prioritise investigative reporting that exposes corrupt practices within institutions as that would help reduce the rate of corrupt practices in Nigeria.

Keywords: Investigative Journalism, Corruption, Institutional Corruption, Journalists, Nigeria

Introduction

Nigeria's ambition to achieve an environment of zero tolerance to corruption depends on the active role of the media, civil society groups; non-governmental organisations and the entire members of the public to facilitate good governance and promote a corrupt free society (Asemah, 2011). In other words, the press and other anti-graft agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) serves as an agent of change, and as the watchdog of the society is expected to play a part in ensuring transparency and accountability in government as well as contribute to the efforts of crime-fighting institutions to curb corruption in the country (Nwuneli, 1990; Nwosu, 1990). They further aver that the media have long been recognised as having a role to play in mitigating corruption in Nigeria. According to Ronning (2009), Nigeria is one of the developing countries struggling with the menace of corruption in the world. He observed that Nigeria, a country with a rich cultural heritage and abundant natural resources, has been plagued by institutional corruption for decades.

In view of the above, Ribadu (2006, p. 122) revealed that "the history of corruption in Nigeria is strongly rooted in the over 29 years of military rule. All the military regimes subdued the rule of law, facilitated the looting of the public treasury, prohibited free speech and instituted a secret culture in the running of government business." He further observed that "the period of this military regime witnessed a total reversal and destruction of every good thing in the country." Corruption became the dominant guiding principle for running affairs of the country. The situation became glaring that when military seized power from democratically elected governments, pervasive corruption was cited as the justification. Corroborating the above statement, Alawole, (2009) averred that corruption not only permeates every facet of government in Nigeria, from the legislative and judicial branches, to the police and civil service but also include non-governmental organisation and private individuals. This according to him has led to a widespread loss of faith in the society which if left unaddressed, will undermine confidence in democracy as a viable system of government.

According to Asemah (2012), investigative journalists play a crucial role in uncovering corruption scandals and bringing them to light. Through their work, they expose corrupt officials and institutions, creating public awareness and putting pressure on authorities to take action. Investigative journalism also helps to build transparency and accountability in government institutions. Despite its importance, investigative journalism faces numerous challenges in Nigeria. Journalists are often threatened or intimidated by those who seek to keep their corrupt practices hidden.

Recent cases of institutional corruption in Nigeria have highlighted the pervasive nature of this problem and its impact on the country's development (Suntai & Shem, 2022). In recent years, Nigeria has been plagued by a series of institutional corruption cases that have left citizens disillusioned and frustrated with the government. The most notable of these cases is the \$2.1 billion arms deal scandal, which involved high-ranking officials in the previous administration diverting funds meant for the purchase of arms to fight Boko Haram insurgents (Eze, 2023). Another case that shook the nation was the

alleged embezzlement of N3 billion from the Federal Government's Social Investment Programme (SIP) by a former minister. This scandal exposed how corruption had infiltrated even programmes designed to alleviate poverty and improve livelihoods (Ukaeje, 2022). Another case is the scandal involving the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), which was accused of mismanaging billions of dollars in oil revenues. Another example is the case of former governor James Ibori, who was convicted in 2012 for embezzling millions of dollars from Delta State (Fotaki, 2020). These cases are just a few examples of how deeply entrenched corruption is in Nigeria's institutions. It is disheartening to see that despite efforts by successive governments to tackle corruption, it continues to thrive. Suffice it to say institutional corruption has become deeply embedded in Nigeria's political and economic systems. The lack of transparency and accountability within these institutions allows corrupt officials to act with impunity, undermining efforts to promote sustainable development and economic growth (Eze, 2023). To combat institutional corruption in Nigeria, there needs to be a concerted effort by the media and all stakeholders-government officials, civil society organisations, and citizens-to hold those responsible accountable for their actions. Only then can we hope for a brighter future where transparency and accountability reign supreme (Ukaeje, 2022; Suntai & Shem). Supporting the above statement, Nwabueze (2010) opines that Journalism can also expose flaws in policy, laws or regulation that foster a climate ripe for corruption, thus creating

Therefore, the study is designed to find out the level of journalists' knowledge of institutional corruption in Taraba State, examine whether journalists in Taraba State employ the use of investigation to combat institutional corruption and investigate the challenges bedevilling journalists in combating institutional corruption in Taraba State focusing on journalists in Jalingo metropolis as area of focus

Research Objectives

The research objectives were to:

1. Find out the level of journalists' knowledge of institutional corruption in Taraba State.
2. Examine whether journalists in Taraba State employ the use of investigation to combat institutional corruption.
3. Investigate the challenges bedevilling journalists in combating institutional corruption in Taraba State.

Conceptual Clarification of Institutional Corruption

Institutional corruption is a term that refers to the systematic and pervasive abuse of power by institutions. This type of corruption can take many forms, including bribery, nepotism, cronyism and favouritism. The concept of institutional corruption has been studied extensively in the fields of sociology, political science and economics (Suntai & Shem, 2018).

According to Enste & Heldman (2017), institutional corruption refers to corrupt practices that are built into the systems, policies and norms of an organisation or

institution. This type of corruption is often more damaging to the institution and society than individual corruption and is commonly obtainable in sectors such as education. It involves behaviour in which individuals in the public or private sector improperly and unlawfully enrich themselves or those close to them, by the misuse of the public power entrusted to them. This corrupt behaviour undermines the ethical standards of society and is often characterised by infrastructural decay, lack of transparency and improper implementation of policies and programmes (Suntai & Shem, 2018).

Similarly, Fotaki (2020) observed that institutional corruption can be regarded as deviations from an institution's original purpose, which may not necessarily be illegal but can cause harm to those who depend on it and create perverse dependencies. He observed further that the theory of institutional corruption stresses the impact of policy incentives and regulation on organisational culture and how they may cause organisations to diverge from their original purpose. Mores so, Lessig (2013) pointed out that institutional corruption is a systemic and strategic influence which is legal or even currently ethical, that undermines the institution's effectiveness by diverting it from its purpose or weakening its ability to achieve its purpose, including, to the extent relevant to its purpose, weakening either the public's trust in that institution or the institution's inherent trustworthiness.

Investigative Journalism

Investigative journalism is a crucial aspect of modern-day journalism, which aims to uncover hidden truths and expose corruption in society. Conceptualising investigative journalism involves understanding the principles and practices that guide this form of reporting (Dogari & Shem, 2017). At its core, investigative journalism involves in-depth research, analysis, and fact-checking to uncover stories that are not readily available or easily accessible. This type of reporting requires a high level of skill, persistence, and dedication to uncover the truth (Suntai & Shem, 2022).

According to Eze (2023), investigative journalism is the practice of uncovering information that is not readily available through routine sources and channels. This implies that Investigative journalism is a form of journalism that seeks to uncover and report on issues that are not commonly known or understood. It involves in-depth research, analysis, and reporting to expose wrongdoing, corruption or other issues of public interest. In addition, Di Salvo (2022) pointed out that the role of investigative journalists is to hold those in power accountable for their actions and decisions.

Theoretical Framework

The social responsibility theory, proposed by Siebert, Peterson & Schramm, asserts that media outlets and journalists have a duty to society and must accept and fulfil certain obligations. This theory is suitable for the study of tackling corruption through investigative journalism because it mandates journalists to investigate corrupt practices and report them accurately, objectively and with balance (Asemah, 2012). The theory emphasises that journalists have a social responsibility to uncover corrupt activities and hold those responsible accountable. Media social responsibility theory and institutional

corruption are two concepts that have been widely discussed in the field of media studies. Media social responsibility theory posits that the media has a duty to serve the public interest by providing accurate and unbiased information, promoting democratic values, and holding those in power accountable. As a result, McQuail (2005) cited in Okocha & Akpe (2022) noted that:

The media have obligations to society and media ownership is a public trust; news media should be truthful, accurate, fair and objective and relevant; the media should be free but self-regulated; the media should follow agreed codes of ethics and professional conduct and under some circumstances, government may need to intervene to safeguard the public interest (p.150)

It is therefore, essential for media outlets to uphold their social responsibility by maintaining high ethical standards and avoiding conflicts of interest. By doing so, they can help combat institutional corruption and promote transparency and accountability in society. Social responsibility philosophy of the mass media implies that the media have a sacred duty to the society and its people. It is important for the interest of the society to be projected ahead of any other interest. Social responsibility theory is relevant to this study as it helps to explain several issues on institutional corruption and facilitate ways of mitigating same through timely, fair, balance and objective reportage. This however forms the basis for the discussion on the role of the media or investigative journalism as a socially responsible institution which acts and contributes to the development of the society by acting as agent of social change in the fight against institutional corruption in Nigeria

Investigative Journalism and Institutional Corruption in Nigeria

Investigative journalism has been defined as a form of journalism in which reporters go in-depth to investigate a single story that may uncover corruption, review government policies or of corporate houses or draw attention to social, economic, political or cultural trends (Hunter, 2012). Investigative journalism involves exposing to the public, matters that are concealed either deliberately by someone in a position of power, or accidentally, behind a chaotic mass of facts and circumstances that obscure understanding (Eze, 2023). In combating corruption, investigative journalism has had a significant impact for over a century. The role of investigative journalism in the fight against corruption lies in exposing public matters that are otherwise concealed, either deliberately or accidentally (Suntai & Shem, 2018).

However, investigative journalism is threatened by numerous challenges which are almost crippling its proper practice (Aretha, & Ben, 2012). It has been observed that media ownership can constrain the powers of investigative journalists when the owners impose policies on the media house (Dogari, Shem & Apuke, 2019). Also, political interference has been identified as a factor contributing to the limitations of investigative journalism in Nigeria (Dogari & Shem, 2017). Despite the auspicious potency of investigative journalism, newspapers, television and radio stations tend to have the same

headlines today, with no serious attempt to uncover new data or produce discoveries (Pali, 2023). There is little indication that Nigeria's long-standing battle with corruption or its global perception of it, has improved in the recent decade (Komolafe, Nkereuwem & Kalu-Amah, 2019). The present administration's and prior administrations' anti-corruption rhetoric has not resulted in significant anti-corruption initiatives, programmes or projects. According to Justine & Egere (2018), exposing individuals who pilfer public monies is akin to warfare in Africa, particularly Nigeria. On the one hand, this has resulted in a lack of rationality in public service, and on the other, underdevelopment. Commenting on Nigeria's sluggish approach to fighting corruption, Justine & Egere (2018) captured it thus:

Bribery and corruption seem to be recurrent decimals in Nigeria. With the culture of impunity in place, there is a massive outcry by Nigerians about the selective fight against corruption. Besides the government's insensitivity to the plight of the masses, which falls on deaf ears, the Nigerian people are often short-changed. Despite the "total" war on corruption by anti-graft institutions like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices and the Related Commission (ICPC) and the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), many alleged cases of corruption are still in the cooler (p.95).

Ronning (2009) noted the foregoing despicable condition described above, the media is the common man's sole hope in the battle against corruption in Nigeria. As a result, it is important to mention that one of the most important players in the battle against corruption is the media. The media is expected to act as a conduit between the government and the people, as well as a societal voice. In other words, one of the professional responsibilities of the media in any society is to serve as a civic watchdog whose duty it is to unearth secrets/issues and hold the government accountable to society (Asemah, 2012).

Functions of Media in Mitigating Institutional Corruption in Nigeria

Media play key roles in investigating allegations of impropriety in public affairs and exposing corruption and corrupt practices (Stapenhurst, 2000). These roles become even more important when existing political institutions are weak and inefficient in ensuring accountability of public servants (World Bank, 1997). Mass media as main expression of public opinion have long been recognised (Coronel, 2009) as having social and constitutional responsibilities in monitoring government, exposing its excesses and ensuring that governments are accountable to the governed. For instance reporting corruption may prompt public bodies to launch formal investigations into allegations of corruption.

According to Kwase & Shem (2017), the mass media performs a vital role in society by examining social maladies and discovering truths previously hidden from the public, and this can only be achieved through investigative journalism, a type of journalistic practice. Gambo (2014), cited in (Edmond & Wilson, 2018) corroborate that

the media has a responsibility to guarantee that the activities of the government and government officials are compatible with these goals.

Commenting on the role of the media in the battle against corruption in recent years, Oyebode (2013) cited in Eze (2023) acknowledged that the media has played a great role thus far, albeit this study maintains that further efforts are needed. Oyebode further summarises the role played by the Nigerian media in the fight against corruption thus: In the recent past, the media have also done well in a few cases. The media followed up on the forgery and perjury cases against former Speaker of the House of Representatives, Alhaji Salishu Buhari and investigated the questionable past of the old senate president, Evan Enwerem. Other cases have been brought against former senate president, Chuba Okadigbo (for financial recklessness) and against former national vice-chairman of the Peoples' Democratic Party, Bode George for contract splitting.

Factors affecting Investigative Performance in Curbing Corruption in Nigeria

According to Nogara (2009) some of the factors affecting media performance in the fight against corruption include: freedom of information, access to information, ownership factor, credibility factor, political factor among others are challenges impeding journalists from performing their social responsibility role to members of the public. Similarly, Yushau (2009) who observed that inadequate working conditions, salaries, training and equipment are challenges impeding investigative journalists in digging deep into corruption related stories.

Methodology

In this study, qualitative research methodology was adopted. The target population for this study consists of active media professionals drawn from six key media organisations operating within Jalingo metropolis: Taraba Television (TTV), Taraba State Broadcasting Service (TSBS), Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), Sunrise, Correspondence Chapel and Rock FM. These organisations represent the main broadcasting and journalism platforms in the state capital, making them highly relevant to the study's focus. While no official staff directory exists across these media houses, informal consultations and preliminary visits revealed that the combined number of active personnel involved in editorial, reporting, and broadcasting roles across the six organisations is 21. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (e)^2}$$

Where,

N = ?

e=0.05 (margin of error at 5%)

N= 21

$$n = \frac{21}{1 + (0.05)^2} = \frac{21}{1 + 0.0025} = 20$$

Hence, the sample size is 20.

A total of 20 participants were selected out of 100 population representing over 90% of the population. The small size of the population itself justifies this large sample proportion. According to Nwana (1981), when the population is small (i.e., below 100), a larger sample size—such as 20% or more—is necessary to capture the diversity of opinions and reduce sampling error. In fact, for populations under 30, as in this case, nearly complete enumeration is often preferred.

Additionally, Babbie (2005) supports the idea that when dealing with small populations, researchers are encouraged to include as many units as possible in order to ensure representativeness. The sample distribution across the media houses was deliberately designed to reflect the operational scale and editorial engagement of each organisation. TTV and TSBS, being the two major state-run broadcast stations with broader staffing and daily programming responsibilities, were allocated 5 respondents each, covering various departments such as news, current affairs, and production. NTA and Sunrise, which are medium-scale operations with consistent but relatively fewer staff involved in active journalism, received 3 respondents each. Correspondence Chapel, a body of field journalists representing various national media outlets and Rock FM, a private radio station with a compact team, were assigned 2 respondents each. This stratified purposive approach ensured fair representation based on the functional presence and activity level of each organisation within the media landscape of Jalingo to address the issue of institutional corruption in Nigeria.

According to Toluhi (2001), qualitative research design is a technique where the researcher asks open-ended questions orally and records the respondents answer. However, the researcher conveniently selected twenty journalists to form the sample of the study. The idea behind selecting twenty (20) journalists was to give room for effective discussion on the subject matter as getting many may affect the desired results as regards sampling responses from journalists who resides in Jalingo metropolis and can respond to issues on investigative journalism in mitigating institutional corruption in Nigeria. The interviewees were members of the Nigeria union of journalists selected from six (6) NUJ chapels in Taraba State. The data collection exercise lasted 3 days that is 31st May-2nd June, 2023. Five (5) of the interviewees were journalists from correspondence chapel who writes for national dailies. According to Toluhi (2001), provides for the researcher to select journalists who writes for different media organisations in Taraba State.

Therefore, twenty (20) journalists were interviewed and are coded as thus: (A-1, to A-20) this was done to give understanding during data analysis and discussion of findings.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Data presentation was based on responses from the interviewees who are journalists who write for different media organisation in Nigeria and are residents in Jalingo, Taraba State.

Demographic Data of Interviewees

Table 1: Bio-data information

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	13	65%
Female	7	35%

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage
30-45	10	50%
46-60	9	45%
60 an above	1	5%
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
National Dailies	7	35%
TTV	3	15%
NTA	5	25%
TSBS	3	15%
Sunrise	2	10%
Location	Frequency	Percentage
Magami	5	25%
Mile 6	3	15%
Kona	2	10%
ATC	5	25%
Nukkai	2	10%
Mayo dasa	3	15%
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma	6	30%
HND/Degree	12	60%
Master	2	10%
PhD	0	0%
Total	20	100%

The above table indicates that 13 participants representing 65% were male, while 7 representing 35% were female. This implies that majority of the respondents were males meaning they had more or better understanding of institutional corruption than the female respondents. The table equally indicates that people between the ages of 30-45 were more than other age brackets among the participants implying that corruption issues are evidently discussed among the youth age bracket and it is a great concern to the younger upcoming generation. Also from the table, participants were made up of journalists from different media organisation; 5 participants from national dailies, 3 reporters from Taraba Television, 5 from Nigeria Television Authority, 3 from Taraba State Broadcasting Service, 2 from Sunrise and 2 from Rock FM, Jalingo. This implies that virtually journalists from the select media have knowledge of institutional corruption and are bothered about the effect which has hampered rapid growth and development of the nation Nigeria. It can also be deduced from the table that most of the respondents were holders of first degree implying that they have adequate knowledge about institutional corruption as it affects most media organisation and the country at large.

RO1: Taraba State Journalists' Knowledge of Institutional Corruption in Nigeria

This theme seeks to find out the level of journalist knowledge of institutional corruption. The findings of the study unravelled that the majority of the journalists that formed the

sample of the study have a generic knowledge of corruption but could not distinguish between institutional corruption and other forms of corrupt practices. The above submission emanated from the manner of response gotten from a senior editor A-9 revealed that:

In my opinion, institutional corruption is a form of corruption that has to do with the embezzlement of public funds by workers in either government or private institutions. For instance, lecturers collect money from students or sex for marks. ...In summary, any form of inducement demanded by an individual or given to him/her to manipulate things is institutional corruption.

A-6 observed that institutional corruption entails:

The abuse of power by an individual in a position of authority for personal gain. This type of corruption is prevalent in government institutions, where officials use their power to manipulate policies and regulations to benefit themselves. ... It is an act of falsifying information or documents for personal gain. This includes forging signatures, altering records, and providing false information on official documents.

A-12 participant who shared a similar opinion captured it thus:

Institutional corruption has to do with accepting bribes or gifts in exchange for favours. This type of corruption is common in business transactions and political campaigns. It can also be the misuse of public resources for personal gain. This includes embezzlement and misappropriation of funds meant for public projects.

A-4 participant who was blunt said:

Let me be honest with you, I cannot specifically tell you what institutional corruption entails but I know what corruption is, so if I see any form of corrupt practice whether institutional or personal I think I should be able to identify it. The thing is corruption is corruption whether institutional or government it remains the same.

From the foregoing, it is apt to infer that there is a misconception among journalists regarding what institutional corruption entails. However, there are quite several journalists that demonstrated a good knowledge of what institutional corruption entails. In his words, one of the reporters A-3 revealed that:

In my opinion, institutional corruption is the misuse of authority by people or groups inside a system. Corruption of this magnitude may exist in any organisation, including government agencies, companies, and educational institutions. Manipulation is a common feature of institutional corruption. Institutional corruption is a pervasive problem in Nigeria, affecting every aspect of society. From the police force to government agencies, corruption has become deeply entrenched in the country's institutions. This has led to a lack of trust in public officials and a sense of hopelessness among citizens.

A-7 participant who also demonstrates an understanding of institutional corruption captured it thus:

One of the most significant examples of institutional corruption in Nigeria is the embezzlement of public funds by government officials. This practice has become so common that it is now considered normal, with many politicians using their positions for personal gain rather than serving the people they were elected to represent. Another example is the widespread bribery and extortion by law enforcement officers. The police force, which should be protecting citizens, often engages in corrupt practices such as demanding bribes from motorists or turning a blind eye to criminal activities for financial gain.

From the foregoing, it is observed that there are a few journalists that have a good understanding of investigative journalism and how it operates.

RO2: Employment of Investigative Journalism to Combat Institutional Corruption

Data from this study revealed that the majority of the journalists from the sample of the study revealed that they do not employ the use of investigative journalism in combating institutional corruption. Most of the journalists revealed that there is a lot of risk associated with investigative journalism practice; therefore, they prefer to report normal news events. In his words, A-15 pointed out that: as a journalist, I know it is imperative to employ the use of investigative reporting to combat institutional corruption. Investigative journalism is a powerful tool that can uncover hidden truths and bring accountability to those in positions of power. However, to be sincere with you I would prefer to play safe by reporting normal news stories. See the risk associated with investigative journalism is enormous hence I would not like to risk my life.

Also, A-18 shares similar sentiments revealed that: in my entire career as a journalist, about thirteen years now, I have not investigated any corrupt case. This does not mean I do not want to do that or that I am lazy but the truth remains that I work for a government outfit where consistent payment of salaries is even a problem. Hence, how and where will I get the resources to investigate corruption cases? The truth remains that investigative journalism requires a significant amount of time, resources and expertise; you cannot just jump into it anyhow without preparing fully.

Similarly, A-10 a sport reporter has a contrary opinion that:

Yes, I employ the use of investigative journalism principles in investigating corruption-related cases. However, you know that it's something you do with caution else it may cost you your life. I have investigated a good number of institutional corrupt cases successfully. ...For instance, I once investigated and reported a case of a secondary school in a certain village here in Taraba where teachers do not come to work and the students were left at the mercy of God's hands.

RO3: Challenges Bedevilling Investigative Journalism Practice Concerning Institutional Corruption

Data obtained from this study revealed that there are enormous extant challenges bedevilling and discouraging journalists from practising investigative journalism. The majority of the interviewees such as A-3, A-11, A-19 and A-16 identified threat, harassment and fear of the unknown, lack of resources, lack of access to quality information from the public and private establishments as some of the core challenges bedevilling effective investigative journalism practice in Nigeria. In his words, A-20 observed that: investigative journalism practice is very risky in Nigeria. One of the major challenges we face is the lack of protection from government and security agencies. We are often threatened and harassed by those we investigate; this is one reason why many journalists want to play it safe by not involving in investigative journalism practice. A-16 shares similar view by saying thus: one of the major challenges is the lack of protection for whistleblowers and journalists who expose corruption. Many journalists have been threatened, harassed or even killed for their work. This creates an atmosphere of fear and intimidation that discourages others from speaking out.

A-14 who has similar but different views revealed that: in my opinion, I think one major challenge we faced as journalists, especially in the area of investigative journalism is the lack of resources and funding to carry out investigations. Many media organisations do not prioritise investigative journalism, so we have to rely on personal funds or external support. Additionally, journalists often face difficulties obtaining information from government officials or institutions involved in corrupt practices. This makes it difficult to investigate and report on corruption cases accurately. Other opinion from A-11, A-17 and A-1 felt their major challenges when carrying out an investigative report are lack of access to information, inadequate working condition, salaries, training and equipment. Interviewees 1 and 4 were of the opinion that despite the existence of the Freedom of Information Act, journalists still do not have access to information especially when investigating cases of institutional corruption.

In his words, A-8 opined that: the major challenge with practising investigative journalism in Nigeria is that corruption is deeply rooted in Nigerian society, making it difficult to get access to information and sources without bribes or favours. Another is there is a culture of impunity where those who commit crimes go unpunished. This makes it difficult for us to hold people accountable for their actions. From the foregoing, it can be inferred that the aforementioned challenges serves as an impediment to effective investigative journalism practice hence the increase in corrupt cases in Taraba State and Nigeria at large. For instance, as revealed by A-3, one of the primary challenges faced by investigative journalists is access to information. Many organisations and individuals are reluctant to share sensitive information, making it difficult for journalists to uncover the truth. Additionally, there are legal restrictions on accessing certain types of information, such as classified document.

Another challenge is funding. Investigative journalism requires significant resources and time commitment, which can be expensive for media outlets that may not have sufficient financial backing. This often leads to a lack of investment in investigative

reporting. This revelation aligns with one of the objectives of the study which seek to find out the challenges affecting journalists in the fight against corruption in Nigeria using journalists in Jalingo metropolis as focal point.

Discussion of Findings

The objectives of this study were to first find out the level of journalists' knowledge of institutional corruption in Taraba State, examine whether journalists in Taraba State employ the use of investigation to combat institutional corruption in Nigeria and investigate the challenges bedeviling journalists in combating institutional corruption in the country.

The first objective sought to find out the level of journalist's knowledge of institutional corruption in Nigeria. The findings established that journalists have a crucial role in exposing corruption and holding institutions accountable. It is vital for journalists to note that institutional corruption can occur when institutions prioritise their interests over the public good, even if no individual within the institution is engaging in illegal or unethical behaviour. For example, a government agency may prioritise the interests of corporations over protecting public health and safety. This finding is consistent with the view of Lessig (2013) who opined that institutional corruption is "a systemic and strategic influence which is legal, or even currently ethical, that undermines the institution's effectiveness by diverting it from its purpose or weakening its ability to achieve its purpose, including, to the extent relevant to its purpose, weakening either the public's trust in that institution or the institution's inherent trustworthiness."

A close examination of the views of three interviewees (A-1, A-4 and A-6) shows that journalists in Taraba State have good knowledge of institutional corruption and have been involved in reporting same as much as possible. Their views validates the idea proposed by Siebert, Peterson & Schramm cited in Asemah (2012) who pointed that the media has a duty to serve the public interest by providing accurate and unbiased information, promoting democratic values and holding those in power accountable. Institutional corruption, on the other hand, refers to the systemic abuse of power within organisations or institutions. Suffice it to say that journalists have a responsibility to uncover not just individual acts of corruption but also the underlying structures that enable it. This, however, corroborates the social responsibility theory of the press which points out the roles of journalist in tackling corruption through investigative journalism because it mandates journalists to investigate corrupt practices and report them accurately, objectively, and with balance (Asemah, 2012). The social responsibility theory emphasises that journalists have a social responsibility to uncover corrupt activities and hold those responsible accountable to the people.

This is corroborated by McQuail as cited in Okocha & Akpe (2022) who submits that this theory is about the obligations of the mass media in the specific areas of accountability and responsibility to the people. The theory places a responsibility on journalists to report truthful, comprehensive and accurate accounts and representative picture of events and occurrences to keep the people fully informed by other forces

outside the ethical prescriptions and also reinforce the rule of the media in keeping the society informed on happenings in the country through timely and objective reportage.

The second objective sought the views of the interviewees on the use of investigative techniques in combating institutional in Nigeria. The study revealed that most journalists do not employ the tactics of investigation to curb institutional corruption in Nigeria. These were the views of interviewee (A-10, A-8, A-7 and A-12) who contended that, they do not employ investigation strategies in digging deep into institutional corruption issues. Their assertion invalidates the view of Alawole (2009) who pointed out that “fighting corruption in Nigeria requires proactive efforts of the media as the role of the media is to investigate and dig deep into incidents of corruption in a professional and ethical manner”. In agreement with current study, it has been observed that credible media often exercise strong influence on the public by playing an important part in revealing improper and unfair administrative procedures or corruption in Nigeria. Interviewees (A-19 and A-20) also said that though they are aware of corruption issues in the country, they do not employ the style of investigation in covering corruption for their media organisation. Besides, A-15 posited that “See the risk associated with investigative journalism is enormous hence I would not like to risk my life.”

This equally aligns with the literature review where it has been established that the media have a crucial role to play in the coverage of institutional corruption stories in Nigeria but the media are faced with issues or challenges that hinders them from performing their social responsibility role as observed by Yushau (2009).

To achieve the third research objective, interviewees were asked of the challenges bedeviling investigative journalists in mitigating institutional corruption in Nigeria. Participants (A-4, A-13, A-1 and A-6) all lamented the challenges impeding them as journalists from reporting institutional corruption issues. The finding of this study revealed that lack of access to information, lack of funds, and intimidation among others are some of the challenges bedeviling investigative journalists in Nigeria. The above findings are in tandem with the opinion of Eze (2023) who revealed that even though investigative journalism is a crucial aspect of the media industry that plays a vital role in keeping the public informed and holding those in power accountable, investigative journalists are face with numerous challenges such as lack of access to information which make their work difficult. A-9 and A-5 also aver that many governments and corporations have become increasingly secretive, making it difficult for us journalists to obtain information necessary for their investigations. This has led to increased reliance on whistleblowers, who often risk their careers or even lives to provide information. This finding also consolidates the work of Suntai & Shem (2023) who revealed that investigative journalists are faced with threat of physical harm or legal action. This can lead to threats, intimidation, and even violence against journalists in attempting to cover corruption issues that bother on institutions in Nigeria.

These challenges as revealed in the study is in agreement with the view of Yushau (2009) who observed that inadequate working conditions, salaries, training and equipment are challenges impeding investigative journalists in digging deep into

corruption related stories. This confirms existing literature that supports the arguments of scholars for investigative journalists serving as surveyor of the environment through timely reports of institutional corruption stories.

Additionally, the researchers discovered that though there are challenges militating against journalists' reportage of corruption stories, stakeholders in media organisations, non-governmental organisations, anti-graft agencies such as EFCC, ICPC, and members of the public are to collaborate with the media to stem the tide or menace of institutional corruption in Nigeria by thereby giving Nigeria a good image in the international community of nations who have a different mindset about Nigeria as a corrupt country. The implication is that the federal government of Nigeria can win the war on any form of corruption if the aforementioned stakeholders and properly engaged to fight the battle of institutional corruption which will facilitate rapid growth and development.

Conclusion

Institutional corruption is a term used to describe the abuse of power by individuals or organisations within a system. Unfortunately, there is a common misconception among journalists that institutional corruption only occurs in government or political institutions. The truth is that institutional corruption exists in all sectors, including healthcare, education and finance. It manifests itself in various forms such as bribery, nepotism, and favouritism. Therefore, journalists must acknowledge the existence of institutional corruption across all sectors and take necessary steps to combat it. This can be achieved through investigative journalism.

In conclusion, the misconception that institutional corruption only exists in government institutions must be dispelled. Generally, institutional corruption undermines democracy and hinders economic development. Nigerian authorities must take decisive action to address this issue and restore public trust in institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Media organisation should initiate programmes aimed at enlightening journalists on what institutional corruption entails. This can be achieved through organising seminars and symposiums from time to time.
2. The Nigeria union of journalists should prioritise investigative reporting that exposes corrupt practices within institutions. This requires thorough research and fact-checking to ensure accuracy and credibility.
3. Journalists should collaborate with other media outlets to amplify their message and reach a wider audience. This can include partnering with other news organisations or utilising social media platforms to share stories.
4. Media organisations, government agencies and news agencies should improve the working conditions and salary structure for journalists. They should be obliged to cover all expenses incurred by journalists rather than relying on sources for bribes and payments

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